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A UFD1L-centered network in basal subtype breast cancer.

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Results

1. UFD1L expression is significantly increased in basal-like breast cancer (GSE45827 and GSE87049).
2. UFD interacts with UBXN family proteins UBXN7 and UBXN10 and VCP.
3. UFD1L is co-regulated with a proteasome network (co-reg SEEK).